

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Genetic Differentiation in *Mytilus* Populations Across Climatic Zones in Greenland

M. Zbawicka¹ | L. Bach² | J. Kotta³ | A. Kaasik³ | K. Herkül³ | M. Małachowicz¹ | R. Wenne¹¹Institute of Oceanology, Polish Academy of Sciences, Sopot, Poland | ²Arctic Research Centre, Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, Roskilde, Denmark | ³Estonian Marine Institute, University of Tartu, Tallinn, Estonia**Correspondence:** M. Zbawicka (mzbawicka@iopan.pl)**Received:** 22 July 2025 | **Revised:** 22 July 2025 | **Accepted:** 6 August 2025**Funding:** This research was funded in part by the 2011/01/B/NZ9/04352 NCN project to R.W. and the statutory task IV.1 in the IO PAS. The majority of the mussel sampling in Greenland was conducted in relation to research projects funded by the Environmental Agency for Mineral Resource Activities (Greenland Government). The authors wish to thank Anders Mosbech, David Boertmann, Rune Dietz, Torkel Gissel, Morten Birch Larsen and Mette Dalgaard for mussel sampling at remote sites in Greenland. J.K., K.H., A.K. and M.Z. were funded by the EU Horizon Europe project MARine Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning leading to Ecosystem Services (MARBEFES, Project ID 101060937). J.K., K.H. and A.K. were funded by EU Horizon Europe project Observing and Mapping Marine Ecosystems—Next Generation Tools (OBAMA-NEXT, Project ID 101081642).**Keywords:** Arctic | environmental variables | hybridisation | mussels | population structure | SNP

ABSTRACT

Aim: One of the major consequences of climate change in the rapidly warming Arctic regions is the decrease in sea-ice extent. This is accompanied by changes in marine chemistry and nutrient dynamics, which in turn drive significant shifts in ecosystems, altering their components and reshaping the interactions between them. Research on genetic differences and grasping the relevance of local adaptation is essential for deepening our knowledge of the effects of environmental changes on Arctic marine organisms, which can inform successful conservation and management. These include environmentally sensitive mussels, widely used for biomonitoring. The study aimed to examine the genetic structure and hybridisation patterns of the *Mytilus* species complex along the Greenland coast and identify environmental factors influencing genotypic composition or signs of local adaptation.

Location: The research includes three climatic zones in Greenland: high arctic, low arctic and subarctic. Extensive sampling was conducted along the understudied coast.

Taxa: *Mytilus* species complex.

Methods: Greenland and reference samples were successfully genotyped using a panel of 79 SNP loci, previously created and verified to distinguish *Mytilus* taxa and identify potential hybridisation. After filtering, 53 annotated SNPs were used to assess genetic diversity, population structure and hybridisation patterns. Regional-scale weather and environmental proxies were obtained from online databases and used in Boosted Regression Tree analyses to identify environmental variables explaining genotypic composition.

Results: Most of the populations from the Greenland coast were identified as pure *M. edulis*. Only the Savissivik population from the north high-Arctic region was formed by pure *M. trossulus*. Six populations from the north and central regions consisted of a mixture of pure *M. trossulus*, pure *M. edulis* or *M. trossulus* × *M. edulis* hybrids, mainly F1. All Greenland populations with *M. edulis* genomes exhibited admixtures with both American and European *M. edulis*, displaying a higher prevalence of the American form, except for the southern sub-Arctic Greenland populations. Linking environmental conditions with genotypes revealed that wave exposure and food availability were most strongly associated with allele variability.

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2025 The Author(s). *Journal of Biogeography* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

Main Conclusions: Large-scale sampling along the Greenland coast revealed a taxon gradient, of *M. trossulus* predominating mainly in the north and *M. edulis* further south. *M. edulis*, *M. trossulus* and their hybrids showed non-random distributions tied to specific niches. The admixture of *M. edulis* from both American and European forms suggests that Arctic coastal benthic ecosystems may serve as an important bridge facilitating connections between populations on both sides of the Atlantic. Environmental factors strongly shape the genetic structure of *Mytilus* spp. in Arctic coastal benthic ecosystems, while geographic location plays a minor role in allele frequency patterns. These findings align with the expectations that ocean currents around Greenland are of great importance for the population distribution of *Mytilus* spp., but local environmental conditions notably shape the populations' genetic structure.

1 | Introduction

The Arctic region is warming nearly four times faster than the global average (Rantanen et al. 2022), driving profound shifts in ecosystems with widespread impacts on species distribution patterns, ecological interactions and productivity in coastal and marine environments (Poloczanska et al. 2013; AMAP 2021; IPCC 2023). This accelerated warming intensifies the melting of ice cover (Post et al. 2013), thus impacting waves (Christakos et al. 2023), chlorophyll concentration (Qu and Gabric 2022), currents (Wei et al. 2024), and leading to salinity decrease (Li and Fedorov 2021). Such changes can profoundly impact animal fitness and may affect the abundance, distribution and physiology of marine organisms (Poloczanska et al. 2013; Molinos García et al. 2016; Blowes et al. 2019). As climate change continues to alter different environmental conditions such as ocean currents in the Arctic region, changes in the connectivity of pelagic species (Puncher et al. 2022) and benthic species with pelagic larval stages (Cowen et al. 2006; Zbawicka et al. 2019) in settlement processes and postlarval mortality are expected to drive significant shifts in marine biodiversity (Renaud et al. 2019; Kotwicki et al. 2021). Assessing the impact of climate change on regional biodiversity can be particularly rewarding through biomonitoring of environmentally sensitive marine mussels such as *Mytilus* spp. Due to their sedentary lifestyle, wide distribution, tolerance to a large range of environmental stressors, as well as their filter feeding behaviour (Mlouka et al. 2019), *Mytilus* spp. has been widely employed as an indicator organism for biomonitoring purposes. This application is not limited to Greenland (Bach 2020; Søndergaard et al. 2020) but extends to global contexts as well (Rainbow et al. 2000; Blackmore and Wang 2003).

Mytilus spp., commonly known as blue mussels, play a vital role in the Arctic intertidal coastal zone ecosystems, including Greenland, whereas it primarily includes two incompletely isolated species: *Mytilus edulis* (Linne, 1758) and *Mytilus trossulus* (Gould, 1850). Recent advanced research revealed that *M. trossulus* invaded the Arctic Ocean from the Pacific Ocean around 3.5 million years ago (mya) through the Bering Strait (Vermeij 1991; Rawson and Hilbish 1995). During glacial periods, the Bering Strait closed and allopatric speciation resulted in the evolution of *M. edulis* in the Atlantic. Since then, *M. edulis* has spread to large parts of the Atlantic, and limited gene flow between populations on either side has led to their genetic divergence (Riginos et al. 2004; Wenne et al. 2020, 2022; Simon et al. 2021). Analysis of mitochondrial DNA suggests that *M. trossulus* reinvaded the Arctic Ocean between 46,000 and 20,000 years ago

just after the last glacial maximum (LGM ~18,000–21,000 years ago) and continued migration after the Bering Strait opening (~10 kya; Rawson and Harper 2009; Šmietanka et al. 2013). From there, it invaded both sides of the Atlantic, resulting in the *M. trossulus*/*M. edulis* hybrid zones along North American and European coasts (Riginos and Cunningham 2005; Väinölä and Strelkov 2011; Zbawicka et al. 2012). Recent genetic research on *Mytilus* species in Greenland describes findings of *M. edulis* in the subarctic and low-Arctic region in South Greenland (60° and 64° N, respectively) and *M. trossulus* in the high-Arctic region at Thule (77° N) on the west coast (Blicher et al. 2013; Mathiesen et al. 2017; Bach et al. 2019; Wenne et al. 2020). A mixing zone of both *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* and hybrids has been documented around 70°–72° N (Wenne et al. 2016; Mathiesen et al. 2017). *M. trossulus* in Greenland likely originated from two sources: the North Pacific for northern populations and the Northwest Atlantic for others (Bach et al. 2019), whereas based on mitochondrial DNA studies, southern populations of *M. edulis* display similarity to Canadian and North America populations (Riginos and Henzler 2008).

The ecology of *Mytilus* spp. in Greenland has been explored with aspects of their biology, distribution and environmental roles (Strand and Asmund 2003; Høgslund et al. 2014; Thyrring et al. 2015). Furthermore, while a growing body of research has emphasised the potential impacts of climate change on blue mussels and their associated ecosystems (Harley et al. 2006; Zippay and Helmuth 2012; Nielsen et al. 2021), studies also pin elements of resilience of *Mytilus* to environmental changes as decreased salinity and increased temperatures (Clark et al. 2021; Barrett et al. 2022). The geographical distribution of *Mytilus* spp. covers three climatic zones: high-Arctic, low-Arctic and sub-Arctic (<https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/greenland/climate-data-historical>). This zonality is largely defined by ice cover and ocean currents, with a relatively warm ocean current running up along the coast of West Greenland that keeps the sea ice-free far to the north. Conversely, a cold and icy current flows along the East Greenland from the far north to the south (Ettema et al. 2010; Riget et al. 2019). The *Mytilus* spp. population genetic structure and their capacity to adapt to environmental challenges is influenced or reflected by a variety of traits, including long pelagic larval durations (PLD) and high anthropogenic dispersal potential, which enable wide gene flow (Segovia et al. 2024). Their genotype-dependent fecundity and temporal variation of spawning in hybrid mussels indicates directional selection (Gardner and Skibinski 1990). High hybridisation potential among *Mytilus* taxa increases genetic diversity and introduces adaptive alleles through introgression, complicating species

boundaries (Wenne et al. 2020; Mathiesen et al. 2017). This might influence shell morphology; for example, hybrids of *M. edulis* with *M. trossulus* produce mussels with weaker shells (Beaumont et al. 2008) more vulnerable to damage. However, shell parameters likely reflect local environmental conditions such as wave energy and salinity (Michalek et al. 2021), thus shell morphology can be a heritable and adaptive trait that influences the survival of mussels. Byssal attachment strength in mussels is also an important trait that may influence or reflect population structure and species-specific climate change effects (Newcomb et al. 2022). Further, phenotypic plasticity might also vary across different local populations and in different *Mytilus* traits (Osoreo et al. 2017). Physiological tolerance, through expression changes of stress proteins and metabolic adjustments, enables *Mytilus* species to survive and adapt to different environmental conditions like warming, acidification and hypoxia (Vasquez et al. 2020). Furthermore, *M. trossulus* shows higher tolerance to colder temperatures and lower salinity than *M. edulis*, suggesting better adaptation to cold high-latitude habitats and brackish environments (Väinölä and Strelkov 2011; Bennike and Wagner 2012; Gill et al. 2023).

Despite ongoing studies on Greenland mussels, the exact geographical area where the species overlap and separate is still unknown, and it cannot be excluded that interspecies patches occur in areas other than those currently studied. The distribution is likely driven by an effect of oceanic current dispersal and limited by species-specific differences in adaptations and tolerances to climatic environmental factors such as salinity, temperature, physical impact including ice cover as well as food availability (Qiu et al. 2002; Wenne et al. 2020). In this study, we performed extensive sampling along Greenland's understudied coast in order to (i) examine the genetic structure of the *Mytilus* species complex, (ii) map the distribution of *Mytilus* taxa along coast, (iii) identify potential hybrids and (iv) conduct detailed analyses of *M. edulis* in Greenland. Furthermore, we aimed to explore environmental factors influencing genotypic composition and signs of local adaptation. By statistically linking genetic structure to key environmental variables in *Mytilus* spp., we aimed to (i) map allele distributions in *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus*, (ii) isolate interspecies genetic differences at sites where both species co-occur and (iii) track within-species shifts in allele frequency across environmental gradients, while also testing whether hybrids occupy a distinct niche. We hypothesised that different *Mytilus* species occupy distinct environmental niches, reflecting species-specific ecological preferences. Additionally, we expected allele frequencies to be significantly associated with key environmental variables, indicating potential signals of local adaptation. Finally, we anticipated that these genotype-environment relationships would differ between species, reflecting their unique adaptive responses to environmental conditions. Together, these steps clarify how local adaptation shapes *Mytilus* communities and their ecological responses.

To address the study's goals, we selected a validated panel of 53 SNPs that has been widely applied across *Mytilus* species with demonstrated power to resolve taxa and hybrid classes (Zbawicka et al. 2012, 2014; Wenne et al. 2016, 2020). The markers are genome-wide, located in non-coding and predominantly in coding regions, making them suitable for detecting both

neutral and potentially adaptive variation. This panel effectively balances marker informativeness with sample size, enabling robust population-level analyses while maintaining comparability with previous studies.

Conducting research on genetic differences among and within species, grasping the relevance of local adaptation and establishing a baseline for the *Mytilus* species complex are essential for deepening our knowledge of the effects of rapid environmental changes on Arctic marine organisms, which can then inform successful conservation and management approaches (Brodersen and Seehausen 2014).

2 | Methods

2.1 | Sample Description and DNA Isolation

A total of 653 *Mytilus* spp. samples, varying in age and size (30 to 50 mm), were collected from 25 locations along the Greenland coast in 2015 (Figure 1, Figure S1, Table 1). These samples were either whole specimens or tissue samples preserved in 96% ethanol. DNA extraction was performed using a modified CTAB method from Hoarau et al. (2002), as follows. Approximately 5 mm³ of mantle tissue was incubated for 45 min at 60°C in 800 µL extraction buffer (100 mM Tris HCl, 1.4 M NaCl, 20 mM ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, 2% CTAB), 2 µL β-mercaptoethanol and 6 U proteinase K, followed by two chloroform separations. DNA was precipitated with 500 µL of ice-cold isopropanol, followed by storage at -20°C for 45 min, and centrifugation (20,000 g) for 20 min at 4°C. The DNA pellet was rinsed with 80% ethanol, washed with 70% ethanol, air-dried and resuspended in 150 µL of sterile-filtered distilled H₂O.

Additionally, 15 reference populations (353 specimens), selected on the basis of previous analyses using the same assay, were included, featuring *M. edulis* from the Atlantic coast of the USA, Canada, Northern Ireland, Scotland and France; *M. galloprovincialis* from the Atlantic coast of Spain and the Mediterranean Sea in Italy; and *M. trossulus* from Atlantic and Pacific Canada, Pacific Ocean and Scotland (Gardner et al. 2016; Wenne et al. 2016, 2020; Zbawicka et al. 2018, 2019; Bach et al. 2019). Four Greenland populations were also included for reanalysis: one from Savissivik (Bach et al. 2019) and three from Maarmorilik, Uummannaq (Wenne et al. 2016; Bach et al. 2019; Wenne et al. 2020; Table 1).

2.2 | Single Nucleotide Polymorphism Development and Genotyping

Putative 385 SNPs were designed based on alignment and comparison of mRNA and DNA sequences with EST Genbank references of *M. trossulus*, *M. edulis* and *M. galloprovincialis* individuals originating from Europe and America (Zbawicka et al. 2012, 2014, 2018; Gardner et al. 2016; Wenne et al. 2016). These SNPs were selected randomly, based on several differences: among pure taxa, within-taxon polymorphisms and polymorphisms observed in hybrid individuals. The potential genomic impact of the SNPs (non-synonymous or synonymous substitution type) was predicted based on the identified open

FIGURE 1 | Legend on next page.

FIGURE 1 | *Mytilus* taxa and hybrids identified in Greenland (pie charts based on results for $K=3$ computed with STRUCTURE, details in Table S7). See Table 1 for details of site codes, numbers of individuals per location and origin. Location shortcuts: SIS (SIS1-6), NUUK (NUUK1-3), IVI (IVI1-3), NAL (NAL1-5), MAARM (GLD, GLL, GLS). Map created using ArcGIS Pro 3.2 software (<http://www.esri.com/en-us/arcgis/products/arcgis-pro/overview>) combined with data diagrams created in Microsoft Excel (<http://www.microsoft.com/>).

reading frames (ORFs). Of all candidate SNPs, 79 were selected based on genotyping quality (positive results for at least 90% of samples) and used in assay development and preliminary tested on 300 specimens of *Mytilus* collected from geographic regions including Europe, North and South America and New Zealand (Zbawicka et al. 2012, 2014).

In total, 1132 individuals from Greenland and from reference populations (Table 1) were genotyped using the Sequenom MassARRAY iPLEX genotyping platform (Gabriel et al. 2009). PCR and extension primers were designed using the Assay Design 3.1 program (Sequenom), then analysed and scored using Typer 3.4 software (Sequenom). SNPs were classified, based on manual inspection, as ‘failed assays’ (meaning that the majority of genotypes could not be scored and/or the samples did not cluster well according to genotype), ‘monomorphic SNPs’ or ‘polymorphic SNPs’. According to these categories, 24 SNPs did not provide an acceptable quality score and 2 were monomorphic in all samples. Based on quality and informativeness, 53 SNPs with a high quality score (above 90%) were filtered from the panel set and used in further analyses (Table S1). To predict possible SNP relationships between *Mytilus* genotypes and environmental factors, sequences were assigned to chromosomes and annotated to genes of the reference *M. trossulus* genome (GCF_036588685.1) using BlastN and verified by BlastX (Altschul et al. 1990) against proteins from the NCBI non-redundant (NR) database (e -value = $1e-20$, similarity > 80%; Table S1). Pathway enrichment analysis was performed using the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) in the Orthology-Based Annotation System (KOBAS v.3.0) (corrected p -value < 0.05; Bu et al. 2021).

2.3 | Genetic Data Analyses

2.3.1 | Genetic Diversity

Population genetic analyses were conducted using Arlequin v.3.5.1.2 (Excoffier and Lischer 2010) to estimate genetic diversity and degree of differentiation among populations (pairwise F_{ST}), proportion of polymorphic SNP loci (P_O), minor allele frequency (MAF), observed (H_O) and expected (H_E) heterozygosity, inbreeding coefficient (F_{IS}) and departures from Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium (HWE). The false discovery rate (FDR-BY) was used to adjust the significance threshold ($\alpha=0.05$) for multiple testing (Benjamini and Yekutieli. 2001; Narum 2006; Diz et al. 2011).

2.3.2 | Population Genetic Structure

A correspondence analysis (Benzécri 1992), executed in GENETIX (Belkhir et al. 2003), was applied to enable visualisation of genetic substructure within Greenland populations

at both population and individual levels. The axes represent the data matrix’s contribution of inertia, analogous to the total variance in allelic frequency. Due to the presence of the mix of two forms of *M. edulis*, American and European, in both North Europe and the Arctic, additional detailed analysis of *M. edulis* was undertaken (Wenne et al. 2020).

Bayesian-based method in STRUCTURE v. 2.3.4 software, assuming admixture, disregarding population affiliation and allowing for correlation of allele frequencies between clusters was used for clustering and assignment testing (Pritchard et al. 2000; Falush et al. 2007). The optimal number of genetic clusters was determined by comparing log-likelihoods for K values from 1 to the study number of populations plus 1, with at least 5 runs for each K value, following method published by Evanno et al. 2005. The burn-in period was 50,000, and 100,000 Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) cycles followed. While a $q \geq 0.9$ threshold value assigned individuals to clusters in STRUCTURE analysis (Tominaga et al. 2018), individuals with q -values between 0.1 and 0.9 were deemed potentially admixed (Lecis et al. 2006). Individuals were considered assigned to a species if the proportion of admixture (STRUCTURE) was $\geq 90\%$. Individuals with values < 90% were identified as putative hybrids between the species that showed the two highest probability membership values.

2.3.3 | Hybridisation and Introgression

We selected 14 SNP markers (marked in Table S1 as HI) with high-frequency alleles in pure *M. trossulus* (approximately 90%–100%, Table S2) for calculating the hybrid index (HI) score, as outlined in Wenne et al. (2016). These markers differentiate *M. trossulus* from *M. edulis* and *M. galloprovincialis*. An HI score of zero represents a ‘pure’ *M. edulis*, while a score of one indicates a ‘pure’ *M. trossulus*. We calculated HI for individuals and average values for each population to evaluate the extent of introgression between *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus*.

We employed NewHybrids v1 (Anderson and Thompson 2002) to estimate the posterior probability of individuals belonging to four genotypic categories, corresponding to hybrid classes: native *M. trossulus*, *M. edulis*, F1 hybrids, and other hybrids (putative F2 and backcrosses). The same 14 SNP markers with high-frequency alleles in pure *M. trossulus* (approximately 90%–100%) used in the HI analysis were chosen for this purpose.

2.3.4 | Modelling Relationships Between Environmental Variables and Allele Frequencies

Regional-scale proxies for weather and environmental conditions were acquired from various online databases (details in

TABLE 1 | Detailed information and genetic parameters of the 44 samples of *Mytilus* mussels. P_O , % of polymorphic loci; H_O , observed heterozygosity; H_E , expected heterozygosity.

Sample name	Localisation	Country	Water area	No. of individuals	P_O	F_{IS}	Loci with HWE departure			H_O	H_E	MAF	Average gene diversity over loci	Average no. of pairwise differences within population	Coordinates	Sample collection
							F_{IS}	HWE	departure							
TAS	Tasiliq	Denmark	Atlantic	29	47.1698	-0.11	2	0.283	0.280	0.089	0.100	5.24	37°15'15.70"W	2015		
NAL1	Nalunaq, Nanortalik	Denmark	Atlantic	30	81.1321	0.25	2	0.148	0.204	0.111	0.141	6.90	44°58'3.62"W	2015		
NAL2	Nalunaq, Nanortalik	Denmark	Atlantic	30	47.1698	0.02	2	0.274	0.295	0.091	0.118	5.93	44°56'56.21"W	2015		
NAL3	Nalunaq, Nanortalik	Denmark	Atlantic	29	45.283	0.05	2	0.283	0.308	0.092	0.135	6.03	44°57'37.00"W	2015		
NAL4	Nalunaq, Nanortalik	Denmark	Atlantic	30	50.9434	-0.04	2	0.282	0.286	0.095	0.135	6.08	44°56'12.60"W	2015		
NAL5	Nalunaq, Nanortalik	Denmark	Atlantic	30	45.283	0.04	2	0.286	0.303	0.091	0.117	5.86	44°55'48.48"W	2015		
NAN	Nanortalik	Denmark	Atlantic	29	47.1698	0.08	1	0.258	0.306	0.096	0.107	5.68	45°14'56.92"W	2015		
IVI1	Ivittut	Denmark	Atlantic	35	52.8302	0.11	3	0.220	0.257	0.086	0.130	5.39	48°10'28.07"W	2015		
IVI2	Ivittut	Denmark	Atlantic	35	58.4906	0.02	1	0.243	0.254	0.099	0.142	6.10	48°9'32.39"W	2015		
IVI3	Ivittut	Denmark	Atlantic	35	54.717	0.06	2	0.239	0.260	0.093	0.137	5.94	48°8'27.66"W	2015		
NUUK1	Nuuk	Denmark	Atlantic	30	45.283	-0.02	2	0.281	0.300	0.089	0.114	5.23	51°29'25.86"W	2015		
NUUK2	Nuuk	Denmark	Atlantic	28	54.717	0.00	2	0.234	0.258	0.095	0.121	5.41	51°23'32.52"W	2015		
NUUK3	Nuuk	Denmark	Atlantic	29	45.283	0.04	2	0.250	0.291	0.084	0.127	5.05	51°40'28.80"W	2015		
ISUA	Isua	Denmark	Atlantic	27	47.1698	0.02	3	0.244	0.282	0.089	0.127	4.86	51°5'29.13"W	2015		
SIS1	Sisimiut	Denmark	Atlantic	12	37.7358	0.03	1	0.335	0.344	0.086	0.129	5.76	53°40'41.37"W	2015		
SIS2	Sisimiut	Denmark	Atlantic	10	39.6226	0.14	1	0.321	0.372	0.098	0.117	5.99	53°39'25.35"W	2015		
SIS3	Sisimiut	Denmark	Atlantic	10	41.5094	-0.01	1	0.321	0.328	0.085	0.110	5.36	53°43'25.77"W	2015		
SIS4	Sisimiut	Denmark	Atlantic	12	41.5094	0.09	1	0.306	0.352	0.095	0.136	6.01	53°40'12.64"W	2015		
SIS5	Sisimiut	Denmark	Atlantic	20	45.283	0.04	1	0.262	0.289	0.087	0.126	5.42	53°45'6.93"W	2015		
SIS6	Sisimiut	Denmark	Atlantic	22	43.3962	0.05	1	0.239	0.275	0.073	0.113	4.83	53°29'00.43"W	2015		
AAS	Aasiaat	Denmark	Atlantic	30	49.0566	-0.02	1	0.250	0.275	0.089	0.069	4.92	52°52'58.46"W	2015		

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

F_{IS} , inbreeding coefficient; values with $p < 0.05$ after Benjamini–Yekutieli correction are marked in bold; MAF, minor allele frequency; #, reanalysed samples

Sample name	Localisation	Country	Water area	No. of individuals	P_O	F_{IS}	Locus with HWE departure	H_0	H_E	MAF	Average gene diversity over loci	Average no. of pairwise differences within population	Coordinates	Sample collection
QEQ	Qeqertarsuaq	Denmark	Atlantic	29	81.1321	0.45	19	0.182	0.354	0.208	0.253	12.29	69°14'45.46"N 53°33'14.65"W	2015
NUUS	Nuussuaq	Denmark	Atlantic	15	39.6226	0.00		0.318	0.337	0.104	0.103	4.74	70°24'25.46"N 53°57'35.86"W	2015
GLL#	Maarmorilik, Uummannaq	Denmark	Atlantic	30	81.1321	0.49	22	0.191	0.387	0.229	0.305	14.15	70°59'42.42"N 52°16'41.37"W	2012
GLS#	Maarmorilik, Uummannaq	Denmark	Atlantic	33	84.9057	0.35	11	0.223	0.381	0.258	0.280	13.75	71°07'56.63"N 51°14'58.81"W	2012
GLD#	Maarmorilik, Uummannaq	Denmark	Atlantic	33	83.0189	0.33	11	0.231	0.375	0.240	0.282	13.45	71°8'42.96"N 51°16'31.99"W	2012
UPE	Upemavik	Denmark	Atlantic	33	86.7925	0.31	10	0.192	0.312	0.191	0.225	11.26	72°47'14.79"N 56°8'51.59"W	2015
SAV#	Savissvik	Denmark	Atlantic	30	41.5094	0.08	1	0.233	0.276	0.147	0.076	4.49	76°1'5.26"N 65°7'4.18"W	2015
QAA	Qaanaq	Denmark	Atlantic	34	81.1321	0.23	6	0.158	0.232	0.132	0.141	7.89	77°27'57.05"N 69°14'17.81"W	2015
IRD	Indian River, Delaware	USA	Atlantic	30	43.3962	0.11		0.235	0.263	0.076	0.112	4.96	36°52'6.19"N 75°58'2.16"W	2012
PBAE	Placentia Bay, New Foundland	Canada	Atlantic	5	28.3019	0.00	1	0.353	0.399	0.068	0.108	5.00	47°2'40.05"N 54°11'34.72"W	2012
LGF	Lough Foyle	North Ireland	Atlantic	28	49.0566	0.06		0.226	0.278	0.093	0.099	5.10	55°5'35.50"N 7°4'48.92"W	2006
LEE	Loch Etive, Scotland	Great Britain	Atlantic	12	35.8491	-0.01		0.310	0.325	0.080	0.120	4.87	56°27'21.35"N 5°18'26.62"W	2008
LOI	Loire	France	Atlantic	30	49.0566	0.10		0.225	0.243	0.083	0.115	5.08	47°14'43.83"N 2°13'48.88"W	2004
ALT	Aleutian Island	USA	Pacific	26	33.9623	0.13	2	0.245	0.298	0.070	0.071	4.19	51°11'47.08"N 179°16'20.79"E	2011
VAN	Vancouver	Canada	Pacific	19	37.7358	0.00	1	0.271	0.298	0.078	0.088	4.73	49°18'33.75"N 123°49'15.41"W	2006
KKAT	Nova Scotia, Halifax	Canada	Atlantic	29	58.4906	0.15	4	0.209	0.261	0.110	0.135	7.11	44°30'33.79"N 63°29'24.91"W	1996
PBAT	Placentia Bay	Canada	Atlantic	9	47.1698	0.29	2	0.202	0.317	0.107	0.134	6.93	47°2'40.05"N 54°11'34.72"W	2012
LET	Loch Etive, Scotland	Great Britain	Atlantic	15	58.4906	0.18	2	0.193	0.267	0.107	0.128	6.78	56°27'21.35"N 5°18'26.62"W	2008

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

F_{IS} , inbreeding coefficient; values with $p < 0.05$ after Benjamini–Yekutieli correction are marked in bold; MAF, minor allele frequency; #, reanalysed samples

Sample name	Localisation	Country	Water area	No. of individuals	P_O	F_{IS}	Loci with HWE departure	H_0	H_E	MAF	Average gene diversity over loci	Average no. of pairwise differences within population	Coordinates	Sample collection
BID	Bidasoa	Spain	Atlantic	30	50.9434	0.03	1	0.324	0.339	0.123	0.149	7.75	43°21'38.71"N 1°51'11.15"W	2004
CAM	Camarinal	Spain	Atlantic	29	47.1698	0.03	1	0.318	0.341	0.119	0.149	7.10	36° 3'30.09"N 5°46'8.88"W	2004
VIG	Vigo	Spain	Atlantic	30	52.8302	0.08	1	0.289	0.316	0.123	0.152	7.65	42°13'54.12"N 8°45'7.22"W	2004
LID	Lido	Italy	Mediterranean Sea	32	52.8302	0.03	1	0.284	0.304	0.108	0.140	7.03	45°30'25.42"N 12°38'30.04"E	2006
ORI	Oristano	Italy	Mediterranean Sea	29	47.1698	-0.01		0.301	0.313	0.099	0.126	6.48	39°47'59.88"N 8°31'9.72"E	2004

1132

Table S3). These climatological time series were employed to characterise typical environmental conditions (i.e., averages) in the regions of interest over extended periods. However, as the environmental datasets were obtained from multiple sources, they resulted in different temporal ranges. These minor differences in dataset timings are considered insignificant, as regional climatological averages change over centuries and millennia rather than a few years. In addition, the spatial resolution of the datasets varied from 0.04° to 2°. To ensure consistency, each variable was resampled onto a common grid at the exact coordinates of our sampling sites; the heterogeneity in native resolutions simply reflects the best model products currently available for the region. Because distances between sampling sites far exceed even the coarsest grid cell, this resampling removes any potential bias and does not compromise the validity of our analyses. However, our focus on large spatial patterns suggests that the granularity of environmental variables is more detailed than required for the study's scope.

Multicollinearity can pose issues in spatial modelling algorithms when determining ecologically relevant environmental variables (Dormann et al. 2013). Therefore, prior to modelling, we assessed multicollinearity using Pearson correlation analysis to exclude highly correlated variables. Most variables showed weak intercorrelations (Figure S2). However, ice cover negatively correlated with cloud cover ($r = -0.88$), solar radiation (-0.82) and air temperature (-0.82); solar radiation positively correlated with air temperature (0.89) and precipitation (0.85); and wave height positively correlated with air temperature (0.93), precipitation (0.95) and solar radiation (0.83). Due to these correlations, the final model excluded air temperature, precipitation, cloud cover and solar radiation. The interpretation of results should, however, consider the potential impact of the excluded variables.

When analysing the correlation patterns between environmental factors and the genetic structure of *Mytilus* spp., our research objectives were as follows. Firstly, we determined the overall distribution of alleles between two species. Hybrids were excluded from the model due to the limited sample size. Here, a binomial mixed model was fitted, treating the study station as a random effect and species as a fixed effect using the R package lme4 (Bates et al. 2015). We then investigated whether there were differences in the proportion of each locus between the species using a likelihood ratio test for detecting statistical significance.

Secondly, we aimed to identify inter-species differences that were independent of environmental factors. Although the initial research question considered data from all stations, the uneven distribution of species across locations—i.e., different species occurred at different stations, and only some stations included all species—necessitated a more targeted approach. Therefore, we included only those stations where more than five specimens of each studied species were available, resulting in a subset of four stations. This allowed for a more accurate assessment of inter-species differences by ensuring sufficient representation per species. The previous model was then re-fitted to this subset of data, ensuring that any observed differences could be strictly attributed to inter-species variation rather than site-specific environmental effects.

The third research question aimed to investigate intra-species shifts in allele distribution across environmental gradients, with a particular emphasis on identifying the allele loci most closely associated with environmental variability. This analysis included data from all sampled stations, allowing us to capture the full range of environmental conditions experienced by each species across their distribution and to detect consistent genotype–environment associations within species. To explore this, Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) analyses were conducted separately for each species. As a sub-question, we examined whether *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* hybrids occupy a specific environmental niche or if hybridisation is unaffected by the environment.

When examining the relationship between environmental factors and allele frequencies in *Mytilus* spp., we analysed individual shells and classified each specimen as either *M. edulis*, *M. trossulus* or their hybrid. Using individual genotypes as a response variable can be problematic due to the presence of pseudoreplication in the predictors, as multiple individuals shared identical sets of environmental variables. We avoided this issue by resampling data from stations with less specimens (to not overemphasise any station) and only calculated variable importances relative to each other (so that any possible pseudoreplication effect would be equal for all environmental variables).

To assess the proportion of variability in allele frequencies attributable to spatial structure rather than environmental predictors, we conducted additional Boosted Regression Tree (BRT) analyses that included geographical coordinates (latitude and longitude) as predictors. By incorporating these spatial variables, we were able to evaluate the extent to which spatial autocorrelation—potentially driven by dispersal or historical processes—contributed to the observed genetic patterns, independently of measured environmental variables.

BRT combines machine learning and statistical modelling strengths, using an algorithm to learn the relationship between the response and its predictors, rather than starting with a data model (Hastie et al. 2009). BRT models generally outperform traditional modelling methods, such as GLM, GAM and multivariate adaptive regression splines (Elith et al. 2006; Leathwick et al. 2006). BRT's performance is comparable, or occasionally superior, to other machine learning methods like Random Forest (RF; Yang et al. 2016). The R package gbm was employed for BRT model fitting, using a Bernoulli loss function for two alleles and a multinomial loss function for three alleles. Model predictions relied on the highest-class probability. The BRT modelling involved first identifying variable impact directions using partial dependence from an unconstrained model, then fitting a constrained model with monotonic effects and recalculating the partial dependence functions. Predictor importance was evaluated by comparing adjusted count pseudo-R-squared values, which reflect each model's predictive accuracy relative to a null model.

Finally, we applied the multinomial log-linear model using the R package nnet (Venables and Ripley 2002) to investigate the variation in proportions of *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* and their hybrid within populations across different environmental gradients. This approach was chosen due to a limitation of the Gradient Boosting Machine in the BRT model, which resulted

in inaccurate output for the multinomial distributions. The R package caret (Kuhn 2008) was used for carrying out 10-fold cross-validation for detecting the optimal decay parameter value (a regularisation value used to safeguard against model overfitting) and assessing the variable importance.

3 | Results

3.1 | Genetic Diversity and Differentiation Among and Within Populations

Mytilus spp. samples collected from 29 locations along the Greenland coast and 15 reference populations were successfully genotyped with 53 filtered and annotated SNPs, which differentiate among the *Mytilus* taxa and identify potential hybridisation (Table 1). Annotation analysis revealed a broad distribution of SNPs across the genome, with localisation on nearly all chromosomes (Table S1). Functional enrichment analysis indicated that most of the SNPs are associated with the ribosome pathway, oxidative phosphorylation, thermogenesis, metabolic pathways and the proteasome (corrected p value < 0.05).

The results of the diversity analyses indicate the occurrence of the highest polymorphism level (P_O), heterozygosity (H_O), MAF values, within and between populations from the northwest coast of Greenland: Maarmorilik fjord and Qeqertarsuaq (Table 1). In addition, the obtained F_{IS} values (ranging from 0.5 to 1) indicate the existence of nearly exclusively two alternative homozygotes, with an absence of heterozygotes in these populations (Table S4).

When comparing MAF values for Greenland *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* (SAV) populations with reference *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* from other regions, the Greenland populations generally displayed higher and more variable values (Table 1, Table S5).

Pairwise F_{ST} values among most of the populations from Greenland were statistically significant after FDR-BY correction (Table S6). The most differentiated populations within Greenland were collected at Savissivik, Maarmorilik Fjord, Qeqertarsuaq and Upernavik locations, where *M. trossulus* individuals were found. However, two groups of populations, *M. edulis* from south Greenland (NAL, IVI) and central (SIS, NUUK, NUUS) parts of Greenland, were mostly homogeneous. Low but statistically significant levels of differentiation were found between *M. edulis* populations from central (AAS, NUUK, SIS) and southern (NAL, NAN, TAS) Greenland.

3.2 | Population Structure and Cluster Analysis

This study analysed the structure of Greenlandic *Mytilus* populations, first with all reference samples and then with smaller groups for greater resolution. Connections among specimens were assessed using a Bayesian model in STRUCTURE software. The STRUCTURE analysis revealed the presence of three main clusters, *M. trossulus*, *M. edulis* and *M. galloprovincialis* ($K=3$; Figure 2a). Twenty populations from Greenland clustered together as *M. edulis*, whilst the population from Savissivik (SAV) clustered with *M. trossulus* populations. Six populations

a

K = 3

b

K = 3

FIGURE 2 | Structure plot ($K=3$) for 29 Greenland mussel populations, *Mytilus* and reference *M. edulis*, *M. trossulus*, *M. galloprovincialis* populations (a), with exclusion of reference *M. galloprovincialis* (b).

from the north and central region (UPE, QAA, GLD, GLL, GLS) showed very high levels of admixture: individuals were assigned to the *M. trossulus* or *M. edulis* cluster with $q \geq 0.9$ or were ambiguously assigned to two of them (q about 0.5 for 12%–33% of individuals). Two exceptions were observed: one individual from Nalunaq was assigned to *M. trossulus* and one individual from Nuuk was ambiguously assigned to the *M. galloprovincialis* and *M. edulis* clusters (with genome admixture values $q=0.763$ for *M. edulis* and $q=0.2324$ for *M. galloprovincialis*) (Table 2). No individuals from Greenland have been fully assigned to the *M. galloprovincialis* cluster.

Due to the presence of only *M. trossulus* and *M. edulis*, additional analyses were performed excluding *M. galloprovincialis* references. The analysis exposed a further division, where the *M. edulis* cluster divided into two distinct groups representing the American and European populations (Figure 2b, Table S7).

A map with pie charts on the structure of the Greenland populations based on the results for $K=3$ is shown in Figure 1.

A Correspondence Analysis (CA) was conducted on all *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* populations, including reference populations from North America and the Atlantic coast of Europe (Figure 3). The first two axes accounted for 94% of the total variation. Axis 1 demonstrated a clear separation between *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus*, while axis 2 separated the European and the American forms of *M. edulis*. The Greenland individuals were grouped with both *M. trossulus* (mainly Pacific form overlapped with Atlantic form), the American form of *M. edulis*, with a slight overlap of the European form and the mixed group between *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus*.

This CA revealed that the *M. edulis* samples formed three groups: American, European and Greenlandic, where the southern

TABLE 2 | Hybrid identification. HI, hybrid index score; V_{HI} , variance of HI; Med., *M. edulis*; Mtr, *M. trossulus*; Mgal, *M. galloprovincialis*; NA, not applicable.

Sample	Site	HI	V_{HI}	<i>M. edulis</i> (%)	<i>M. trossulus</i> (%)	Structure $K = 3$			NewHybrids							
						<i>M. galloprovincialis</i> (%)	<i>M. edulis</i> (%)	<i>M. trossulus</i> (%)	Mix Med/ Mtr (%)	Mix Med/ Mgal (%)	<i>M. edulis</i> (%)	<i>M. trossulus</i> (%)	F1 hybrids (%)	Others hybrids (%)	All hybrids (%)	
TAS	Tasilaq	0.0341	0.0273	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
NAL1	Nalunaq, Nanortalik	0.0692	0.1784	97	3.3	0	0	0	0	0	97	3.3	0	0	0	0
NAL2	Nalunaq, Nanortalik	0.0507	0.0359	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
NAL3	Nalunaq, Nanortalik	0.0441	0.0350	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
NAL4	Nalunaq, Nanortalik	0.0534	0.0323	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
NAL5	Nalunaq, Nanortalik	0.0341	0.0331	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
NAN	Nanortalik	0.0549	0.0331	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
IV11	Ivituut	0.0516	0.0333	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0.0
IV12	Ivituut	0.0633	0.0486	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0.0
IV13	Ivituut	0.0557	0.0443	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0.0
NUUK1	Nuuk	0.0594	0.0380	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
NUUK2	Nuuk	0.0691	0.0610	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
NUUK3	Nuuk	0.0582	0.0465	96.6	0	0	0	0	0	3.4	100	0	0	0	0	0
ISUA	Isua	0.0731	0.0518	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
SIS1	Sisimiut	0.0396	0.0365	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
SIS2	Sisimiut	0.0522	0.0576	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
SIS3	Sisimiut	0.0523	0.0482	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
SIS4	Sisimiut	0.0586	0.0394	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
SIS5	Sisimiut	0.0472	0.0239	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
SIS6	Sisimiut	0.0289	0.0326	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0
AAS	Aasiaat	0.0491	0.0522	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

Sample	Site	HI	V _{HI}	Structure K = 3			Mix			NewHybrids			
				M. edulis (%)	M. trossulus (%)	M. galloprovincialis (%)	M. edulis (%)	M. trossulus (%)	M. galloprovincialis (%)	M. edulis (%)	M. trossulus (%)	F1 hybrids (%)	Others hybrids (%)
QEQ	Qeqertarsuaq	0.7355	0.3641	17.2	62.1	0	20.7	0	17.2	62.1	13.8	6.9	20.7
NUUS	Nuussuaq	0.0712	0.0538	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0
GLL	Maarmorilik	0.3926	0.4088	56.7	26.7	0	16.7	0	56.7	26.7	13.3	3.3	16.7
GLS	Maarmorilik	0.6085	0.3732	24.2	42.4	0	33.3	0	24.2	42.4	18.2	15.2	33.4
GLD	Maarmorilik	0.6610	0.3799	21.2	48.5	0	30.3	0	21.2	48.5	24.2	6.1	30.3
UPE	Upernavik	0.7776	0.3223	12.1	63.6	0	24.2	0	12.1	63.6	21.2	3.0	24.2
SAV	Savissivik	0.9855	0.0227	0	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0
QAA	Qaanaaq	0.9100	0.2031	2.9	85.3	0	11.8	0	2.9	82.4	8.8	5.9	14.7
	References												
	<i>M. edulis</i>	0.0087	0.0189	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0
	<i>M. trossulus</i>	0.9798	0.0236	0	100	0	0	0	0	100	0	0	0
	<i>M. galloprovincialis</i>	NA	NA	0	0	100	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

FIGURE 3 | Correspondence Analysis (CA) of *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* populations from Greenland, including reference populations from North America and the Atlantic coast of Europe. Population codes are as shown in Table 1.

populations grouped together, distinct from central populations (Figure 4a,b). CA on individuals revealed that Greenland specimens formed a tight cluster, slightly overlapping and positioned between the more dispersed American and European reference groups (Figure 4b). Some South Greenland individuals grouped with the European *M. edulis* form, and some individuals from the west-central coast of Greenland grouped with the American form. A subsequent CA on the 22 Greenland populations, excluding reference groups, revealed geographic separation between southern and central Greenland populations along axis 1 (Figure S3).

3.3 | Identification of *M. trossulus* and *M. edulis* Hybrids

As the STRUCTURE and CA analysis identified a number of potential *M. trossulus* and *M. edulis* hybrids (5.6% of all Greenland individuals) across six populations, additional testing was conducted to determine their status (F1, or other hybrids). Pure *M. trossulus* and *M. edulis* were used as reference samples. *M. galloprovincialis* was excluded from further analysis since only one individual (NUUK3) was potentially admixed with *M. galloprovincialis* (0.13% of individuals, according to STRUCTURE analysis, Table 2). The values of hybrid index (*HI*) varied from 0.03 in Sisimiut with the lowest proportion of *M. trossulus* characteristic alleles to 0.98 in Savissivik that had the highest proportion of *M. trossulus* characteristic alleles (Table 2). Most of the Greenland populations were characterised by very low *HI* values (0.03–0.07). Twenty-one populations from Greenland were identified as pure *M. edulis* by both Structure and NewHybrids with an *HI* below 0.075 (after excluding one mix individual from NUUK3). The population from Savissivik (*HI*=0.98) was the only population identified as pure *M. trossulus*, as in the previous analyses.

For the six mixed populations from the north and central region (UPE, QEQ, QAA, GLD, GLL, GLS), the *HI* varied from 0.39 for populations from Maarmorilik (GLL) to 0.91 in a population from Qaanaaq (QAA), and the V_{HI} (variance of *HI*) was very high, reaching 0.41 in the GLL population. Most of the individuals from these 6 populations were identified as pure *M. trossulus* or pure *M. edulis* by both STRUCTURE and NewHybrids. The others were identified as *M. trossulus* \times *M. edulis* hybrids using both STRUCTURE (*q* value about 0.5) and NewHybrids. The NewHybrid analysis revealed mainly F1 hybrids in these 6 populations with a probability over 0.9, and other hybrids were much rarer. The most F1 hybrids were found commonly (>20% of individuals in the population) in the populations from Maarmorilik (GLD) and Upernavik (UPE). The lowest number of hybrids (8.8%) was found in the population from the very most north Qaanaaq (QAA) where the individuals mainly were *M. trossulus* (Table 2). In the vast majority of hybrids (over 80%), it was the American form of *M. edulis* that was identified (Figure 2b).

3.4 | Modelling Relationships Between Environmental Variables and Allele Frequencies

The analysis of the overall allele distribution among species indicates that the species under study were genetically distinct (at $p < 0.05$), with only 6 loci not showing different proportions. When examining general inter-species differences independent of environmental factors, 10 loci did not distinguish between groups. However, the overall pattern clearly demonstrates that the groups were genetically distinct (at $p < 0.05$).

When assessing intra-species allele distribution changes across environmental gradients, we found that the explanatory power of environmental variables for allele distribution was generally low. This was indicated by very small R^2 values

FIGURE 4 | Correspondence analysis (CA) of *M. edulis* populations from Greenland, including reference populations from North America and the Atlantic coast of Europe. Each dot is a population (a) or an individual (b). Population codes are as shown in Table 1.

for many loci. However, exceptions were noted for a few loci where the environment accounted for some variation in allele frequencies. For *M. edulis*, the loci BM21B_G, BM21C_C and BM9C_A were found to be associated with environmental variables such as chlorophyll a concentration, temperature,

tidal range and wind conditions. Likewise, *M. trossulus* allele frequencies at loci BM12C_T, BM30C_A, BM33B_A, BM44B_A, BM44B_G and BM9B_A were associated with environmental conditions, which involved multiple environmental variables such as water chlorophyll-a, silica, nitrate

and phosphorus concentrations, as well as salinity, ice, swell and wind conditions. Stronger winds were found to be correlated with an increased likelihood of the above alleles for both *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* (Table 3). Conversely, higher levels of chlorophyll a were associated with a decreased likelihood of these alleles. The data revealed species-specific responses, with *M. edulis* alleles being less likely to occur with an increasing tidal range, while *M. trossulus* exhibited higher allele frequencies under higher ice cover (Figure S4).

Furthermore, the distribution of *M. edulis*, *M. trossulus* and their hybrids was non-random, indicating their presence in specific environmental niches. Environmental factors showed a significant association with the proportions of species, with the model accounting for 57% of the total variability. The key variables driving this variability were water chlorophyll-a content, wave height and swell height. *M. edulis* was more frequently found in areas with higher chlorophyll-a concentrations and more substantial wave and swell conditions, while *M. trossulus* was found in environments with lower chlorophyll-a levels and less intense wave and swell conditions. As for the hybrids, they had the highest likelihood of occurrence at mid-range chlorophyll-a values. Similar to *M. trossulus*, the probability of discovering hybrids decreased as wave and swell conditions increased (Figure 5). Notably, the allele–environment relationships described in the previous paragraph also explain interspecific differences at stations where all species co-occur, supporting their role in species-specific environmental responses. In general, the role of spatial structure in explaining allele frequency variation was limited. Environmental predictors contributed the majority of the explained variation for both species. For *M. trossulus*, spatial variables accounted for an average of 20% of the variation in allele frequencies, while for *M. edulis* this figure was slightly higher at 37%. The remaining variation was explained by environmental predictors, indicating that environmental forcing played a more dominant role than spatial structure in shaping the genetic patterns observed. Environmental variables data for 29 *Mytilus* populations and their individual allele presences are provided in Table S8.

4 | Discussion

Approach used in this study combines genetic research (SNPs) with environmental data, using machine learning methods to emphasise the multifactorial nature of *Mytilus* species distribution. Through geographically comprehensive sampling along the Greenland coast, we investigated spatial genetic variability in populations of the *Mytilus* species complex in this Arctic region. Our results revealed a clear latitudinal taxon gradient with *M. edulis* domination in the southern regions of Greenland, while *M. trossulus* is more abundant in the north. Furthermore, a characteristic bimodal hybrid zone was revealed, primarily consisting of pure individuals with a large number of F1 hybrids that occur in contact areas. Our integrative approach, combining genotypes with environmental variables, revealed that the population structure of the *Mytilus* species complex in Greenland is strongly influenced by environmental gradients, with wave and chlorophyll conditions emerging as the primary ecological predictors of taxon and hybrid distribution. Moreover, we found a few alleles that correlated with environmental factors such as temperature, wave exposure, ice cover and food supply.

4.1 | Distribution and Population Structure of *Mytilus* Taxa on the Coasts of Greenland

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of the genetic diversity, population genetic structure, geographic distribution and hybridisation of the *Mytilus* species complex in Greenland. Due to ongoing climate changes that induced shifts in Arctic marine ecosystems (AMAP 2021), this research establishes a baseline data for understanding the biogeographic and evolutionary dynamics of key benthic species. The application of a suite of methods for population genetic relationships assessment and grouping (STRUCTURE, CA and HI) revealed that the Greenland populations of *Mytilus* mussels are characterised by a latitudinal taxon gradient along the coast, with *M. trossulus* predominating mainly in the north and *M. edulis* further south. This pattern is consistent with previous observations in Arctic and sub-Arctic zones, where thermal tolerance influences species boundaries (Mathiesen et al. 2017; Nielsen et al. 2021). The ocean current transporting warmer waters from the south to the north along the western coast of Greenland facilitates the northward expansion of *M. edulis* from the sub-arctic and low-arctic regions to the high-arctic. Additionally, it transports *M. trossulus* not only farther north within the high-arctic zone but also into the inner waters of the Greenland fjords. The interior waters of fjords are exposed to lower temperatures and lower salinity caused by the inflow of water from melting glaciers. Conversely, the ocean current carrying cold Arctic waters along the eastern coast of Greenland towards the south-west obstructs the potential northward expansion of *M. edulis*, thereby confining its distribution on the eastern coast solely to its southernmost region (subarctic and arctic zones).

These two *Mytilus* species hybridised in the contact area and created hybrid zones with mixed populations characterised mainly by pure individuals with a large number of hybrids, mainly of the F1 type. This type of hybridisation (bimodal) is characteristic for the European Arctic and the North American Atlantic sub-arctic (Newfoundland) region (Wenne et al. 2020). The visible intensification of hybridisation in Greenland may suggest the influence of environmental factors such as the warm North Atlantic current that facilitate larval dispersal (Berge et al. 2005; Mathiesen et al. 2017). Interestingly, the highest levels of polymorphism were observed in areas (above 69° N) where hybridisation between *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* occurs, highlighting the potential role of hybridisation in shaping the genetic structure and dynamics of Arctic coastal benthic ecosystems. This finding is consistent with previous research on other marine species, indicating that hybridisation could play a significant role in determining the structure and resilience of coastal benthic ecosystems (Bierne et al. 2003; Riginos and Cunningham 2005). Nonetheless, the predominance of pure *Mytilus* individuals and the limited occurrence of later-generation hybrids indicate possible low fertility or reduced fitness. A similar phenomenon has been described for *Mytilus* populations in Arctic Europe, White and Barents Sea (Wenne et al. 2020).

Moreover, our study revealed that the genetic composition of *M. edulis* populations in Greenland appears to exhibit an admixture of both American and European lineages, with a

TABLE 3 | Models relating environmental variables to intra-specific allele frequencies: Total variability explained by each model and relative contribution of best performing environmental variables in describing allele frequencies. The red colour denotes allele models that explained more than 10% of the total variability, and the green colour denotes individual predictor variables that contributed more than 10% of the explained variance.

Allele model	Total variability explained	Chlorophyll	Ice	Nitrate	Phosphate	Salinity	Silicate	Swell	Temperature	Tide	Wave	Wind
<i>M. edulis</i>												
BM147A_T	6.4	55	5	2	8	1	1	5	11	4	0	9
BM21B_G	20.5	23	6	7	2	21	1	7	11	7	0	16
BM21C_C	16.2	11	6	5	8	6	8	8	10	17	2	19
BM5D_T	7.1	12	10	14	4	13	10	11	7	6	1	12
BM61A_C	3.8	16	12	3	4	19	18	2	10	12	0	3
BM9C_A	11.7	32	9	5	3	2	3	5	24	10	2	6
<i>M. trossulus</i>												
BM12C_T	20	12	14	4	9	4	42	4	4	4	0	4
BM30C_A	20	7	8	5	10	37	10	1	3	5	0	13
BM33B_A	14.3	5	18	5	13	4	13	21	8	4	0	8
BM38B_G	11.4	42	2	6	5	8	17	5	6	5	0	5
BM44B_A	26.7	17	30	2	2	22	10	1	0	2	0	15
BM44B_G	20.3	7	6	14	1	15	14	2	8	5	0	28
BM9B_A	16.2	3	1	5	2	80	2	0	0	2	0	5
BM9B_G	5.6	15	9	6	4	33	20	3	4	3	0	4

FIGURE 5 | Key environmental variables associated with *M. edulis*, *M. trossulus* and their hybrids (water chlorophyll content, wave height and swell height) along with the response functions.

generally higher prevalence of the American form. In contrast, European populations from Scandinavian and the Arctic, also with *M. edulis* genomes, showed a predominance of the European form (Wenne et al. 2020). Biogeographically, individuals from central Greenland show higher similarity to the American form, while those from the southeastern and southwestern coasts cluster more closely with the European form. These findings highlight the potential role of Arctic coastal benthic ecosystems in Greenland as a trans-Atlantic bridge, facilitating migration and linking populations from both sides of the Atlantic (Reid et al. 2007; Bach et al. 2019). In contrast, the populations of *M. trossulus* from the northern part of the west coast of Greenland are predominantly similar to the populations found in the North Pacific American region, which is most likely its origin after occasional post-glacial long-distance dispersal across the Bering Strait (Bach et al. 2019). Additionally, the higher MAF values observed across all Greenland populations compared to reference populations may indicate the presence of mixed individuals not only between *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* but also within one taxon, potentially indicating hybridisation between North Pacific and Atlantic populations of *M. trossulus* as well as between the American with European populations of *M. edulis*.

The findings of the current study, along with other recent genetic analyses on *Mytilus* mussels in the Arctic, particularly in Europe and Greenland, offer new insights into the complex dynamics of coastal benthic ecosystems in this region (Zbawicka et al. 2012; Wenne et al. 2016). The analysis of SNPs variability in the Greenland populations highlights a previously unrecognised level of genetic diversity in the region, and we can gain insights into the mechanisms underpinning the observed changes, thereby enabling the development of informed conservation and management strategies (Wassmann and Reigstad 2011).

4.2 | Relationships Between *Mytilus* Genotypes and Environmental Factors

This study aimed to explore the influence of contemporary environmental conditions on the connectivity and local adaptation that define the genetic structure of these organisms. Obtained results demonstrated that the population structure of

the *Mytilus* species complex in Greenland is shaped by multiple environmental variables, with wave conditions (wave and swell height) and food availability (chlorophyll-a levels) emerging as the primary predictors of the distribution of *M. edulis*, *M. trossulus* and their hybrids, aligning with patterns reported in previous studies (Johannesson and André 2006; Sanford and Kelly 2011; Gosling 2015). Rapid changes in the frequencies of alleles diagnostic for both species were observed, notably at wave heights of 1.5–2.5 m, swell heights of 1.5–2 m and chlorophyll-a concentrations of 0.5–1 mg m⁻³, predicting a transition from *M. edulis* to *M. trossulus*. The model predicted contact and hybrid zones mainly to occur under low wave and swell conditions and at chlorophyll-a concentrations of 0.9–1.1 mg m⁻³. These results suggest that trophic linkages between ocean currents, waves and the availability of nutrients and phytoplankton biomass (measured by chlorophyll-a concentration) lead to spatial heterogeneity in habitat, which in turn influences the genetic structure of mussel populations along the Greenland coast. Alterations in ocean currents have the potential to alter larval dispersal patterns, leading to shifts in connectivity and, consequently, genetic structure (Cowen and Sponaugle 2009). However, ocean currents not only drive larval transport but also influence local wave regimes and possess the ability to alter wave characteristics, including their amplitude and direction (Gelderloos et al. 2021; Altiparmaki et al. 2024). Furthermore, ocean currents determine phytoplankton dynamics (via nutrient delivery and advection) which reflects in spatial chlorophyll-a variability (Qu 2015; Vernet et al. 2021). Since mussels are filter feeders, relying on suspended phytoplankton as a primary food resource, their availability determines their growth and survival (Strohmeier et al. 2015; Pantea et al. 2024). Ultimately, shifting environmental conditions can alter selection pressures, promoting local adaptation in marine organisms and shaping population genetic composition (Reusch et al. 2005).

At the allele level, the influence of environmental variables on distribution varied significantly among species and individual alleles. When examining changes in the distribution of alleles within species across environmental gradients, we observed that environmental factors generally had a limited impact on allele distribution. However, certain alleles showed a clear association with environmental variability. Although there was no universal set of predictors across the allele models in *Mytilus*

populations, within each species, allele models showed some similarities. The alleles that were most critical for differentiation and adaptation to environmental changes were those with strong and consistent correlations with factors such as water temperature, salinity, tidal regimes, ice cover, wind and wave conditions and availability of nutrients and food. These factors accounted for the majority of the variability in the probability of allele occurrence (Wenne et al. 2020). Several studies investigated coding-region SNPs as potential drivers of adaptive divergence in response to marine environmental variation (Guo et al. 2023; Nascimento-Schulze et al. 2023). In this study, we identified a few loci annotated as ribosomal proteins genes (BM9B, BM9C, BM12C, BM21B, BM21C, BM30C, BM44B) and cytochrome c oxidase (BM33B), putatively associated with environmental variables such as nutrient availability (chlorophyll-a, nitrate and phosphorus concentrations), as well as salinity, ice, swell and wind conditions in *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus* (Table 3). All of these SNPs are located in coding regions which can alter protein function, reinforcing a causal link between genotype and adaptation (Table S1). Ribosomal proteins, beyond their essential role in ribosome structure and function, exhibit other functions, for example, activate the tumour suppressor p53 pathway in response to ribosomal stress (Zhou et al. 2015) and might also show environmental responsiveness in marine organisms (Tomanek 2011; Gleason et al. 2023; Son et al. 2023). Cytochrome c oxidase, a final oxidase in mitochondrial electron transport involved in the oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) process and was previously related to responses to microplastics (Ortiz-Moriano et al. 2024) and ocean acidification (Todgham and Hofmann 2009).

In more temperate environments, such as the Baltic Sea, previous research has shown strong correlations between the genetic structure of *Mytilus* spp. and environmental conditions. This is particularly evident along the salinity gradient (Riginos and Cunningham 2005; Kijewski et al. 2019). However, when salinity is not a limiting factor for *Mytilus* species, other environmental parameters, such as the wetness gradient defined by air temperature, tidal range and wave intensity, become crucial (Riginos and Cunningham 2005; Bennike and Wagner 2012). Furthermore, research has demonstrated that *M. trossulus*, a cold-water species, is favoured over *M. edulis* when ice cover is present due to their differing phenologies (Toro et al. 2002, 2006). As demonstrated in the current study, changes in the distribution of *M. edulis*, *M. trossulus* and their hybrids, as well as variations in allele frequencies of these species, can occur over small geographical distances (< 50 km), which is significantly less than the potential dispersal distance of their planktonic larvae. The presented findings provide compelling evidence of local selection and adaptation and suggest that the genetic structure of *Mytilus* spp. populations in Arctic coastal benthic ecosystems is significantly impacted by environmental factors, such as water movement (tidal range and wave energy) and physical disturbance (such as ice scour; Figure S5).

The fast changes in allele frequencies observed within narrow ranges of environmental variables highlight the importance of these specific environmental conditions for the adaptation and survival of *Mytilus* spp. in the Arctic coastal benthic ecosystems. These rapid shifts in genetic composition along environmental gradients may indicate that the populations are finely tuned

to specific environmental conditions (Sanford and Kelly 2011; Pespeni et al. 2013; Kijewski et al. 2019). The observed opposite responses also suggest alternative adaptive strategies within *Mytilus* spp. populations. Such contrasting patterns of allele frequency responses have been previously documented in other marine organisms and may be indicative of the presence of trade-offs between different adaptive traits (Levitan et al. 2011; Pespeni et al. 2013).

The striking differences in allele frequencies between studied sites further suggest that even in the presence of strong connectivity among habitats, mussels maintain alleles that are better suited for varying conditions such as high vs. low energy shores (wave height), different probability of desiccation (wetness gradient defined by tidal range), and mechanical disturbance caused by ice scour. However, the precise mechanisms that favour certain alleles in particular environments remain unclear at present. The low spatial structuring observed in *Mytilus* spp. suggests that geographic location has a limited influence on allele frequency patterns, with environmental predictors playing the primary role in shaping population structure—particularly in *M. trossulus*. It is important to note that our analysis assessed statistical associations rather than causal mechanisms, and the spatial component may partly reflect environmental drivers not captured in the current study. However, this is likely only if biotic factors, such as species interactions or localised recruitment dynamics, exert a significant influence since the study already included all major abiotic predictors known to affect *Mytilus* spp. distribution and adaptation. Further research is needed to build on these findings and to investigate the underlying molecular mechanisms and ecological consequences of these adaptive processes in the context of rapidly changing Arctic coastal benthic environments. One approach could be to employ advanced genomic tools, such as population genomics and landscape genetics, to detect the effects of environmental gradients on gene flow and adaptive variation in Arctic marine organisms (Riginos et al. 2016). For this purpose, methods that target a large number of SNPs, such as reduced-representation sequencing techniques like RAD-seq (Restriction-site Associated DNA sequencing) and GBS (Genotyping-by-Sequencing) or whole genome sequencing (WGS) might be used in future studies. Furthermore, studies that investigate the adaptive capacity of marine organisms to rapidly changing environments will be essential in predicting their responses to climate change and developing effective conservation strategies (Somero 2010).

5 | Conclusion

In conclusion, understanding the genetic structure of key Arctic species, such as the blue mussel *Mytilus* species complex in Greenland, and the influence of environmental variables on connectivity and local adaptation, is crucial for predicting and mitigating the impacts of climate change on Arctic marine ecosystems. Genetic analysis, presented in this study, based on geographically extensive sampling along Greenland's coast, revealed a pronounced latitudinal gradient: *M. edulis* dominates the southern regions, while *M. trossulus* is more prevalent in the north. These species overlap in a well-defined hybrid zone, characterised by a bimodal pattern of mostly pure individuals with F1 hybrids. Additionally, we observed that Greenland's *M.*

edulis populations display an intermediate genetic profile between American and European forms, suggesting Greenland may act as a biogeographic bridge between these lineages. Furthermore, analysis revealed that environmental variables, especially wave exposure and chlorophyll concentration, emerged as primary ecological drivers influencing the spatial distribution and hybridisation patterns of *Mytilus* species. Our integrative approach revealed correlations between specific alleles in ribosomal proteins and cytochrome c oxidase with environmental factors such as temperature, ice cover, wave energy and food availability. These findings underscore the adaptive role of environmental factors in shaping genetic composition and species boundaries in Arctic benthic communities. The observed patterns of genetic connectivity among regions, coupled with the prevalence of hybridisation, highlight the complexity of the processes shaping the genetic structure of these ecosystems. Collectively, these results emphasise the multifactorial nature of *Mytilus* species distribution, where different factors shape population structure.

Author Contributions

M.Z. and R.W. designed the research project. M.Z., L.B., A.K., K.H., J.K., M.M., R.W. performed the investigation. M.Z. carried out the laboratory work. M.Z., L.B., A.K., K.H., J.K., M.M. were responsible for the methodology. M.Z., L.B., J.K., M.M. prepared figures and tables. All authors contributed to data analysis and interpretation, and the writing of the paper. M.Z., L.B., A.K., K.H., J.K., M.M., revised subsequent versions and accepted final version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded in part by the 2011/01/B/NZ9/04,352 NCN project to R.W. and the statutory task IV.1 in the IO PAS. The majority of the mussel sampling in Greenland was conducted in relation to research projects funded by the Environmental Agency for Mineral Resource Activities (Greenland Government). The authors wish to thank Anders Mosbech, David Boertmann, Rune Dietz, Torkel Gissel, Morten Birch Larsen and Mette Dalgaard for mussel sampling at remote sites in Greenland. J.K., K.H., A.K. and M.Z. were funded by the EU Horizon Europe project MARine Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning leading to Ecosystem Services (MARBEFES, Project ID 101060937). J.K., K.H. and A.K. were funded by EU Horizon Europe project Observing and Mapping Marine Ecosystems—Next Generation Tools (OBAMA-NEXT, Project ID 101081642).

Disclosure

Sampling and Field Studies: All necessary permits for sampling and observational field studies have been obtained by the authors from the competent authorities and are mentioned in the acknowledgements, if applicable.

Ethics Statement

All applicable international, national and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals were followed by the authors.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that supports the findings of this study is available in the [Supporting Information](#) of this article.

References

- Altiparmaki, O., Ø. Breivik, L. Aouf, et al. 2024. “Influence of Ocean Currents on Wave Modeling and Satellite Observations: Insights From the One Ocean Expedition.” *Journal of Geophysical Research, Oceans* 129: e2024JC021581. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JC021581>.
- Altschul, S. F., W. Gish, W. Miller, E. W. Myers, and D. J. Lipman. 1990. “Basic Local Alignment Search Tool.” *Journal of Molecular Biology* 215, no. 3: 403–410. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2836\(05\)80360-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2836(05)80360-2).
- AMAP. 2021. *Arctic Climate Change Update 2021: Key Trends and Impacts. Summary for Policy-Makers*, 16. Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP).
- Anderson, E. C., and E. A. Thompson. 2002. “A Model-Based Method for Identifying Species Hybrids Using Multilocus Genetic Data.” *Genetics* 160: 1217–1229. <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/160.3.1217>.
- Bach, L. 2020. *Environmental Monitoring at the Nalunaq Gold Mine, South Greenland, 2004–2020*. Vol. 76, 386. <http://dce2.au.dk/pub/SR386.pdf>. Aarhus University, DCE—Danish Centre for Environment and Energy.
- Bach, L., M. Zbawicka, J. Strand, and R. Wenne. 2019. “*Mytilus trosulus* in NW Greenland Is Genetically More Similar to North Pacific Than NW Atlantic Populations of the Species.” *Marine Biodiversity* 49: 1053–1059. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12526-018-0870-0>.
- Barrett, N. J., J. Thyrring, E. M. Harper, et al. 2022. “Molecular Responses to Thermal and Osmotic Stress in Arctic Intertidal Mussels (*Mytilus Edulis*): The Limits of Resilience.” *Genes* 13, no. 1: 155. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes13010155>.
- Bates, D., M. Maechler, B. Bolker, and S. Walker. 2015. “Fitting Linear Mixed-Effects Models Using Lme4.” *Journal of Statistical Software* 67, no. 1: 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v067.i01>.
- Beaumont, A. R., M. P. Hawkins, F. L. Doig, I. M. Davies, and M. Snow. 2008. “Three Species of *Mytilus* and Their Hybrids Identified in a Scottish Loch: Natives, Relicts and Invaders?” *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 367, no. 2: 100–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2008.08.021>.
- Belkhir, K., P. Borsa, L. Chikhi, N. Raufaste, and F. Bonhomme. 2003. “GENETIX Version 4.04, Logiciel Sous Windows Pour la Genetique Des Populations.” In *Laboratoire Genome, Populations, Interactions: CNRS UMR 5000*. Université de Montpellier II, Montpellier.
- Benjamini, Y., and D. Yekutieli. 2001. “The Control of the False Discovery Rate in Multiple Testing Under Dependency.” *Annals of Statistics* 29: 1165–1188. <https://doi.org/10.1214/aos/1013699998>.
- Bennike, O., and B. Wagner. 2012. “Holocene Range of *Mytilus edulis* in Central East Greenland.” *Polar Record* 49: 291–296. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0032247412000277>.
- Benzécri, J. P. 1992. “Correspondence Analysis Handbook.” In *Statistics: A Series of Textbooks and Monographs*, edited by N. Balakrishnan, W. R. Schucany, and P. R. Garvey, vol. 125. Marcel Dekker.
- Berge, J., G. Johnsen, F. Nilsen, B. Gulliksen, and D. Slagstad. 2005. “Ocean Temperature Oscillations Enable Reappearance of Blue Mussels *Mytilus edulis* in Svalbard After a 1000 Year Absence.” *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 303: 167–175. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps303167>.
- Bierne, N., F. Bonhomme, and P. David. 2003. “Habitat Preference and the Marine-Speciation Paradox.” *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences* 270, no. 1527: 1399–1406. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2003.2404>.
- Blackmore, G., and W. X. Wang. 2003. “Comparison of Metal Accumulation in Mussels at Different Local and Global Scales.” *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 22: 388–395. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.5620220221>.
- Blicher, M. E., M. K. Sejr, and S. Hogslund. 2013. “Population Structure of *Mytilus Edulis* in the Intertidal Zone in a Sub-Arctic Fjord, SW

- Greenland." *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 487: 89–100. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps10317>.
- Blowes, S. A., S. R. Supp, L. H. Antão, et al. 2019. "The Geography of Biodiversity Change in Marine and Terrestrial Assemblages." *Science* 366: 339–345. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaw1620>.
- Brodersen, J., and O. Seehausen. 2014. "Why Evolutionary Biologists Should Get Seriously Involved in Ecological Monitoring and Applied Biodiversity Assessment Programs." *Evolutionary Applications* 7: 968–983. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eva.12215>.
- Bu, D., H. Luo, P. Huo, et al. 2021. "KOBAS-i: Intelligent Prioritization and Exploratory Visualization of Biological Functions for Gene Enrichment Analysis." *Nucleic Acids Research* 49, no. W1: W317–W325. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab447>.
- Christakos, K., G. Lavidas, Z. Gao, and J.-V. Björkqvist. 2023. "Long-Term Assessment of Wave Conditions and Wave Energy Resource in the Arctic Ocean." *Renewable Energy* 218: 119678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.119678>.
- Clark, M. S., L. S. Peck, and J. Thyrring. 2021. "Resilience in Greenland Intertidal *Mytilus*: The Hidden Stress Defense." *Science of the Total Environment* 767: 144366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144366>.
- Cowen, R. K., C. B. Paris, and A. Srinivasan. 2006. "Scaling of Connectivity in Marine Populations." *Science* 311, no. 5760: 522–527. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1122039>.
- Cowen, R. K., and S. Sponaugle. 2009. "Larval Dispersal and Marine Population Connectivity." *Annual Review of Marine Science* 1: 443–466. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.marine.010908.163757>.
- Diz, A. P., A. Carvajal-Rodriguez, and D. O. F. Skibinski. 2011. "Multiple Hypothesis Testing in Proteomics: A Strategy for Experimental Work." *Molecular & Cellular Proteomics* 10: M110.004374. <https://doi.org/10.1074/mcp.o110.004374>.
- Dormann, C. F., J. Elith, S. Bacher, et al. 2013. "Collinearity: A Review of Methods to Deal With It and a Simulation Study Evaluating Their Performance." *Ecography* 36: 27–46. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0587.2012.07348.x>.
- Elith, J., C. H. Graham*, R. P. Anderson, et al. 2006. "Novel Methods Improve Prediction of Species' Distributions From Occurrence Data." *Ecography* 29: 129–151. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2006.0906-7590.04596.x>.
- Ettema, J., M. R. Van den Broeke, E. Van Meijgaard, and W. J. Van de Berg. 2010. "Climate of the Greenland Ice Sheet Using a High-Resolution Climate Model—Part 2: Near-Surface Climate and Energy Balance." *Cryosphere* 4, no. 4: 529–544.
- Evanno, G., S. Regnaut, and J. Goudet. 2005. "Detecting the Number of Clusters of Individuals Using the Software STRUCTURE: A Simulation Study." *Molecular Ecology* 14: 2611–2620. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2005.02553.x>.
- Excoffier, L., and H. E. L. Lischer. 2010. "Arlequin Suite Ver 3.5: A New Series of Programs to Perform Population Genetics Analyses Under Linux and Windows." *Molecular Ecology Resources* 10: 564–567. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-0998.2010.02847.x>.
- Falush, D., M. Stephens, and J. K. Pritchard. 2007. "Inference of Population Structure Using Multilocus Genotype Data: Dominant Markers and Null Alleles." *Molecular Ecology Notes* 7: 574–578. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-8286.2007.01758.x>.
- Gabriel, S., L. Ziaugra, and D. Tabbaa. 2009. "SNP Genotyping Using the Sequenom MassARRAY iPLEX Platform." *Current Protocols in Human Genetics* 60: 2–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/0471142905.hg0212s60>.
- Gardner, J. P., M. Zbawicka, K. M. Westfall, and R. Wenne. 2016. "Invasive Blue Mussels Threaten Regional Scale Genetic Diversity in Mainland and Remote Offshore Locations: The Need for Baseline Data and Enhanced Protection in the Southern Ocean." *Global Change Biology* 22, no. 9: 3182–3195. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13332>.
- Gardner, J. P. A., and D. O. F. Skibinski. 1990. "Genotype-Dependent Fecundity and Temporal Variation of Spawning in Hybrid Mussel (*Mytilus*) Populations." *Marine Biology* 105: 153–162. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01344281>.
- Gelderloos, R., T. W. N. Haine, and M. Almansi. 2021. "Coastal Trapped Waves and Other Subinertial Variability Along the Southeast Greenland Coast in a Realistic Numerical Simulation." *Journal of Physical Oceanography* 51: 861–877. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-20-0239.1>.
- Gill, L. T., J. R. Kennedy, and K. E. Marshall. 2023. "Proteostasis in Ice: The Role of Heat Shock Proteins and Ubiquitin in the Freeze Tolerance of the Intertidal Mussel, *Mytilus Trossulus*." *Journal of Comparative Physiology. B* 193: 155–169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00360-022-01473-2>.
- Gleason, L. U., F. J. Fekete, R. L. Tanner, and W. W. Dowd. 2023. "Multi-Omics Reveals Largely Distinct Transcript- and Protein-Level Responses to the Environment in an Intertidal Mussel." *Journal of Experimental Biology* 226, no. 22: jeb245962. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.245962>.
- Gosling, E. 2015. *Marine Bivalve Molluscs*. John Wiley and Sons. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119045212.ch3>.
- Guo, F., Y. Ye, K. Zhu, et al. 2023. "Genetic Diversity, Population Structure, and Environmental Adaptation Signatures of Chinese Coastal Hard-Shell Mussel *Mytilus Coruscus* Revealed by Whole-Genome Sequencing." *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24, no. 17: 13641. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms241713641>.
- Harley, C. D. G., A. Randall Hughes, K. M. Hultgren, et al. 2006. "The Impacts of Climate Change in Coastal Marine Systems." *Ecology Letters* 9, no. 2: 228–241. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2005.00871.x>.
- Hastie, T., R. Tibshirani, and J. Friedman. 2009. "Overview of Supervised Learning." In *The Elements of Statistical Learning*. Springer Series in Statistics.
- Hoarau, G., A. D. Rijnsdorp, H. W. Van Der Veer, W. T. Stam, and J. L. Olsen. 2002. "Population Structure of Plaice (*Pleuronectes Platessa* L.) in Northern Europe: Microsatellites Revealed Large-Scale Spatial and Temporal Homogeneity." *Molecular Ecology* 11, no. 7: 1165–1176. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-294X.2002.01515.x>.
- Høgslund, S., M. K. Sejr, J. Wiktor Jr., M. E. Blicher, and S. Wegeberg. 2014. "Intertidal Community Composition Along Rocky Shores in South-West Greenland: A Quantitative Approach." *Polar Biology* 37, no. 11: 1549–1561. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-014-1541-7>.
- IPCC. 2023. "Synthesis Report of the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), Longer Report." <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/sixth-assessment-report-cycle/>.
- Johannesson, K., and C. André. 2006. "Life on the Margin: Genetic Isolation and Diversity Loss in a Peripheral Marine Ecosystem, the Baltic Sea." *Molecular Ecology* 15, no. 8: 2013–2029. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2006.02919.x>.
- Kijewski, T., M. Zbawicka, J. Strand, et al. 2019. "Random Forest Assessment of Correlation Between Environmental Factors and Genetic Differentiation of Populations: Case of Marine Mussels *Mytilus*." *Oceanologia* 61: 131–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceano.2018.08.002>.
- Kotwicki, L., J. M. Weslawski, M. Włodarska-Kowalczyk, et al. 2021. "The Re-Appearance of the *Mytilus* spp. Complex in Svalbard, Arctic, During the Holocene: The Case for an Arrival by Anthropogenic Flotsam." *Global and Planetary Change* 202: 103502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2021.103502>.
- Kuhn, M. 2008. "Building Predictive Models in R Using the Caret Package." *Journal of Statistical Software* 28, no. 5: 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v028.i05>.
- Leathwick, J. R., J. Elith, M. P. Francis, T. Hastie, and P. Taylor. 2006. "Variation in Demersal Fish Species Richness in the Oceans Surrounding New Zealand: An Analysis Using Boosted Regression

- Trees." *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 321: 267–281. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps321267>.
- Lecis, R., M. Pierpaoli, Z. S. Biro, et al. 2006. "Bayesian Analyses of Admixture in Wild and Domestic Cats (*Felis silvestris*) Using Linked Microsatellite Loci." *Molecular Ecology* 15: 119–132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2005.02812.x>.
- Leviton, D. R., N. D. Fogarty, J. Jara, K. E. Lotterhos, and N. Knowlton. 2011. "Genetic, Spatial, and Temporal Components of Precise Spawning Synchrony in Reef Building Corals of the *Montastraea Annularis* Species Complex." *Evolution* 65, no. 5: 1254–1270. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1558-5646.2011.01235.x>.
- Li, H., and A. V. Fedorov. 2021. "Persistent Freshening of the Arctic Ocean and Changes in the North Atlantic Salinity Caused by Arctic Sea Ice Decline." *Climate Dynamics* 57: 2995–3013. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00382-021-05850-5>.
- Mathiesen, S. S., J. Thyrring, J. Hemmer-Hansen, et al. 2017. "Genetic Diversity and Connectivity Within *Mytilus* spp. in the Subarctic and Arctic." *Evolutionary Applications* 10: 39–55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eva.12415>.
- Michalek, K., D. L. Vendrami, M. Bekaert, et al. 2021. "Mytilus Trossulus Introgression and Consequences for Shell Traits in Longline Cultivated Mussels." *Evolutionary Applications* 14, no. 8: 2085–2100. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eva.13245>.
- Mlouka, R., J. Cachot, S. Sforzini, et al. 2019. "Molecular Mechanisms Underlying the Effects of Temperature Increase on *Mytilus* sp. and Their Hybrids at Early Larval Stages." *Science of the Total Environment* 688: 135200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.135200>.
- Molinos García, J., B. S. Halpern, D. S. Schoeman, et al. 2016. "Climate Velocity and the Future Global Redistribution of Marine Biodiversity." *Nature Climate Change* 6: 83–88. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2769>.
- Narum, S. R. 2006. "Beyond Bonferroni: Less Conservative Analyses for Conservation Genetics." *Conservation Genetics* 7: 783–787. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10592-005-9056-y>.
- Nascimento-Schulze, J. C., T. P. Bean, C. Peñaloza, et al. 2023. "SNP Discovery and Genetic Structure in Blue Mussel Species Using Low Coverage Sequencing and a Medium Density 60K SNP-Array." *Evolutionary Applications* 16, no. 5: 1044–1060. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eva.13552>.
- Newcomb, L. A., A. F. Cannistra, and E. Carrington. 2022. "Divergent Effects of Ocean Warming on Byssal Attachment in Two Congener Mussel Species." *Integrative and Comparative Biology* 62, no. 3: 700–710. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/icac111>.
- Nielsen, M. B., T. K. Vogensen, J. Thyrring, J. G. Sørensen, and M. K. Sejr. 2021. "Freshening Increases the Susceptibility to Heat Stress in Intertidal Mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) From the Arctic." *Journal of Animal Ecology* 90, no. 6: 1515–1524. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.13472>.
- Ortiz-Moriano, M. P., E. Garcia-Vazquez, and G. Machado-Schiaffino. 2024. "Genes of Filter-Feeding Species as a Potential Toolkit for Monitoring Microplastic Impacts." *Aquatic Toxicology* 270: 107234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquatox.2024.107234>.
- Osores, S. J. A., N. A. Lagos, V. San Martin, et al. 2017. "Plasticity and Inter-Population Variability in Physiological and Life-History Traits of the Mussel *Mytilus Chilensis*: A Reciprocal Transplant Experiment." *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 489: 65–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2017.02.005>.
- Pantea, E. D., D. M. Roşioru, and N. Roşoiu. 2024. "Food Availability on Influence Mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (Lamarck, 1819) on Physiological and Biochemical Status." *Annals of the Academy of Romanian Scientists Series on Biological Sciences* 13, no. 1: 7–23. <https://doi.org/10.56082/annalsarscibio.2024.1.7>.
- Pespeni, M. H., E. Sanford, B. Gaylord, et al. 2013. "Evolutionary Change During Experimental Ocean Acidification." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 110, no. 17: 6937–6942. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1220673110>.
- Poloczanska, E., E. S. Poloczanska, C. J. Brown, et al. 2013. "Global Imprint of Climate Change on Marine Life." *Nature Climate Change* 3: 919–925. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1958>.
- Post, E., U. S. Bhatt, C. M. Bitz, et al. 2013. "Ecological Consequences of Sea-Ice Decline." *Science* 341, no. 6145: 519–524. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1235225>.
- Pritchard, J. K., M. Stephens, and P. Donnelly. 2000. "Inference of Population Structure Using Multilocus Genotype Data." *Genetics* 155: 945–959. <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/155.2.945>.
- Puncher, G. N., A. Hanke, D. Busawon, et al. 2022. "Individual Assignment of Atlantic Bluefin Tuna in the Northwestern Atlantic Ocean Using Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms Reveals an Increasing Proportion of Migrants From the Eastern Atlantic Ocean." *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 79: 111–123. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjfas-2020-0336>.
- Qiu, J. W., R. Tremblay, and E. Bourget. 2002. "Ontogenetic Changes in Hyposaline Tolerance in the Mussels *Mytilus Edulis* and *M. trossulus*: Implications for Distribution." *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 228: 143–152. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps228143>.
- Qu, B. 2015. "Chlorophyll a Ice Cover, and North Atlantic Oscillation." In *The Impact of Melting Ice on the Ecosystems in Greenland Sea*. SpringerBriefs in Environmental Science: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-54498-9_2.
- Qu, B., and A. J. Gabric. 2022. "The Multi-Year Comparisons of Chlorophyll and Sea Ice in Greenland Sea and Barents Sea and Their Relationships With the North Atlantic Oscillation." *Journal of Marine Systems* 232: 103749. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2022.103749>.
- Rainbow, P. S., M. Wolowicz, W. Fialkowski, B. D. Smith, and A. Sokolowski. 2000. "Biomonitoring of Trace Metals in the Gulf of Gdansk, Using Mussels (*Mytilus Trossulus*) and Barnacles (*Balanus Improvisus*)." *Water Research* 34, no. 6: 1823–1829. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(99\)00345-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(99)00345-0).
- Rantanen, M., A. Y. Karpechko, A. Lipponen, et al. 2022. "The Arctic Has Warmed Nearly Four Times Faster Than the Globe Since 1979." *Communications Earth & Environment* 3: 168. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00498-3>.
- Rawson, P. D., and F. M. Harper. 2009. "Colonization of the Northwest Atlantic by the Blue Mussel, *Mytilus trossulus* Postdates the Last Glacial Maximum." *Marine Biology* 156: 1857–1868. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-009-1218-x>.
- Rawson, P. D., and T. J. Hilbish. 1995. "Evolutionary Relationships Among the Male and Female Mitochondrial DNA Lineages in the *Mytilus Edulis* Species Complex." *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 12: 893–901. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.molbev.a040266>.
- Reid, P. C., D. G. Johns, M. Edwards, M. Starr, M. Poulin, and P. Snoeijs. 2007. "A Biological Consequence of Reducing Arctic Ice Cover: Arrival of the Pacific Diatom *Neodenticula Seminae* in the North Atlantic for the First Time in 800 000 Years." *Global Change Biology* 13: 1910–1921. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2007.01413.x>.
- Renaud, P. E., P. Wallhead, J. Kotta, et al. 2019. "Arctic Sensitivity? Suitable Habitat for Benthic Taxa Is Surprisingly Robust to Climate Change." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 6: 538. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00538>.
- Reusch, T. B., A. Ehlers, A. Hämmerli, and B. Worm. 2005. "Ecosystem Recovery After Climatic Extremes Enhanced by Genotypic Diversity." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 102, no. 8: 2826–2831. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0500081102>.
- Riget, F. F., A. Mosbech, D. Boertmann, et al. 2019. "The Seas Around Greenland: An Environmental Status and Future Perspective, Europe,

- The Americas and West Africa. Red/Charles Sheppard. Bind 1 2. Udg." In *World Seas: An Environmental Evaluation*, vol. 1, 45–68. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-805068-2.00001-2>.
- Riginos, C., E. D. Crandall, L. Liggins, P. Bongaerts, and E. A. Trembl. 2016. "Navigating the Currents of Seascape Genomics: How Spatial Analyses Can Augment Population Genomic Studies." *Current Zoology* 62, no. 6: 581–601. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cz/zow067>.
- Riginos, C., and C. W. Cunningham. 2005. "Local Adaptation and Species Segregation in Two Mussel (*Mytilus Edulis* × *Mytilus Trossulus*) Hybrid Zones." *Molecular Ecology* 14: 381–400. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2004.02379.x>.
- Riginos, C., and C. M. Henzler. 2008. "Patterns of mtDNA Diversity in North Atlantic Populations of the Mussel *Mytilus edulis*." *Marine Biology* 155, no. 4: 399–412. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-008-1038-4>.
- Riginos, C., M. J. Hickerson, C. M. Henzler, and C. W. Cunningham. 2004. "Differential Patterns of Male and Female mtDNA Exchange Across the Atlantic Ocean in the Blue Mussel, *Mytilus Edulis*." *Evolution* 58: 2438–2451. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0014-3820.2004.tb00873.x>.
- Sanford, E., and M. W. Kelly. 2011. "Local Adaptation in Marine Invertebrates." *Annual Review of Marine Science* 3, no. 1: 509–535. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-120709-142756>.
- Segovia, N. I., D. Coral-Santacruz, and P. A. Haye. 2024. "Genetic Homogeneity and Weak Signatures of Local Adaptation in the Marine Mussel *Mytilus chilensis*." *Scientific Reports* 14: 21081. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-71944-9>.
- Simon, A., C. Fraïsse, T. el Ayari, et al. 2021. "How Do Species Barriers Decay? Concordance and Local Introgression in Mosaic Hybrid Zones of Mussels." *Journal of Evolutionary Biology* 34: 208–223. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jeb.13709>.
- Śmietanka, B., M. Zbawicka, T. Sańko, R. Wenne, and A. Burzyński. 2013. "Molecular Population Genetics of Male and Female Mitochondrial Genomes in Subarctic *Mytilus trossulus*." *Marine Biology* 160: 1709–1721. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-013-2223-7>.
- Somero, G. N. 2010. "The Physiology of Climate Change: How Potentials for Acclimatization and Genetic Adaptation Will Determine 'Winners' and 'Losers'." *Journal of Experimental Biology* 213, no. 6: 912–920. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.037473>.
- Son, H.-J., G. Kang, W. S. Woo, et al. 2023. "Antimicrobial Activity of Identified Ubiquitin-40S Ribosomal Protein S27a (RPS27A), Ubiquitin-Like Protein Fubi, and Ribosomal Protein (S30FAU) in the Starry Flounder (*Platichthys stellatus*)." *Fishes* 8, no. 4: 187. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fishes8040187>.
- Søndergaard, J., A. S. Hansson, L. Bach, et al. 2020. "Environmental Monitoring at Mine Sites in Greenland." In *A Review of Research and Monitoring Practices and Their Role in Minimising Environmental Impact*, vol. 44, 364. <http://dce2.au.dk/pub/SR364.pdf>. Aarhus University, DCE—Danish Centre for Environment and Energy.
- Strand, J., and G. Asmund. 2003. "Tributyltin Accumulation and Effects in Marine Molluscs From West Greenland." *Environmental Pollution* 123: 31–37. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0269-7491\(02\)00361-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0269-7491(02)00361-5).
- Strohmeier, T., Ø. Strand, M. Alunno-Bruscia, et al. 2015. "Response of *Mytilus Edulis* to Enhanced Phytoplankton Availability by Controlled Upwelling in an Oligotrophic Fjord." *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 528: 137–152. <https://doi.org/10.3354/MEPS11036>.
- Thyrring, J., S. Rysgaard, M. E. Blicher, and M. K. Sejv. 2015. "Metabolic Cold Adaptation and Aerobic Performance of Blue Mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) Along a Temperature Gradient Into the High Arctic Region." *Marine Biology* 162: 235–243. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-014-2575-7>.
- Todgham, A. E., and G. E. Hofmann. 2009. "Transcriptomic Response of Sea Urchin Larvae (*Strongylocentrotus purpuratus*) to CO₂-Driven Seawater Acidification." *Journal of Experimental Biology* 212, no. 16: 2579–2594. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.032540>.
- Tomanek, L. 2011. "Environmental Proteomics: Changes in the Proteome of Marine Organisms in Response to Environmental Stress, Pollutants, Infection, Symbiosis, and Development." *Annual Review of Marine Science* 3: 373–399. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-120709-142729>.
- Tominaga, A., M. Matsui, N. Yoshikawa, K. Eto, and K. Nishikawa. 2018. "Genomic Displacement and Shift of the Hybrid Zone in the Japanese Fire-Bellied Newt." *Journal of Heredity* 109: 232–242. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhered/esx085>.
- Toro, J., R. J. Thompson, and D. Innes. 2006. "Fertilization Success and Early Survival in Pure and Hybrid Larvae of *Mytilus edulis* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *M. trossulus* (Gould, 1850) From Laboratory Crosses." *Aquaculture Research* 37: 1703–1708. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2109.2006.01610.x>.
- Toro, J. E., R. J. Thompson, and D. Innes. 2002. "Reproductive Isolation and Reproductive Output in Two Sympatric Mussel Species (*Mytilus edulis*, *M. trossulus*) and Their Hybrids From Newfoundland." *Marine Biology* 141: 897–909. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-002-0897-3>.
- Väinölä, R., and P. Strelkov. 2011. "Mytilus trossulus in Northern Europe." *Marine Biology* 158: 817–833. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-010-1609-z>.
- Vasquez, M. C., D. A. Martinez, and L. Tomanek. 2020. "Multiple Stressor Responses Are Regulated by Sirtuins in *Mytilus* Congeners." *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology. Part A, Molecular & Integrative Physiology* 244: 110719. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpa.2020.110719>.
- Venables, W. N., and B. D. Ripley. 2002. *Modern Applied Statistics With S. Fourth Edition*. Springer.
- Vermeij, G. J. 1991. "Anatomy of an Invasion: The Trans-Arctic Interchange." *Paleobiology* 17: 281–307. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0094837300010617>.
- Vernet, M., I. Ellingsen, C. Marchese, et al. 2021. "Spatial Variability in Rates of Net Primary Production (NPP) and Onset of the Spring Bloom in Greenland Shelf Waters." *Progress in Oceanography* 198: 102655. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.POCEAN.2021.102655>.
- Wassmann, P., and M. Reigstad. 2011. "Future Arctic Ocean Seasonal Ice Zones and Implications for Pelagic-Benthic Coupling." *Oceanography* 24, no. 3: 220–231. <https://doi.org/10.5670/oceanog.2011.74>.
- Wei, X., C. Wilson, S. Bacon, and B. Barton. 2024. *Variability in the Arctic Ocean Currents During 1990–2100*, 14–19. EGU General Assembly. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-6019>.
- Wenne, R., L. Bach, M. Zbawicka, J. Strand, and J. H. McDonald. 2016. "A First Report on Coexistence and Hybridization of *Mytilus Trossulus* and *M. Edulis* Mussels in Greenland." *Polar Biology* 39: 343–355. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-015-1785-x>.
- Wenne, R., M. Zbawicka, L. Bach, et al. 2020. "Trans-Atlantic Distribution and Introgression as Inferred From Single Nucleotide Polymorphism: Mussels *Mytilus* and Environmental Factors." *Genes* 11, no. 5: 530. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes11050530>.
- Wenne, R., M. Zbawicka, A. Prądzińska, et al. 2022. "Molecular Genetic Differentiation of Native Populations of Mediterranean Blue Mussels, *Mytilus Galloprovincialis* Lamarck, 1819, and the Relationship With Environmental Variables." *European Zoological Journal* 89: 755–784. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24750263.2022.2086306>.
- Yang, R.-M., G. L. Zhang, F. Liu, et al. 2016. "Comparison of Boosted Regression Tree and Random Forest Models for Mapping Topsoil Organic Carbon Concentration in an Alpine Ecosystem." *Ecological Indicators* 60: 870–878. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.08.036>.
- Zbawicka, M., A. Drywa, B. Śmietanka, and R. Wenne. 2012. "Identification and Validation of Novel SNP Markers in European Populations of Marine *Mytilus* Mussels." *Marine Biology* 159: 1347–1362. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-012-1915-8>.

Zbawicka, M., J. P. A. Gardner, and R. Wenne. 2019. "Cryptic Diversity in Smooth-Shelled Mussels on Southern Ocean Islands: Connectivity, Hybridisation and a Marine Invasion." *Frontiers in Zoology* 16: 32. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12983-019-0332-y2>.

Zbawicka, M., T. Sanko, J. Strand, and R. Wenne. 2014. "New SNP Markers Reveal Largely Concordant Clinal Variation Across the Hybrid Zone Between *Mytilus* spp. in the Baltic Sea." *Aquatic Biology* 21: 25–36. <https://doi.org/10.3354/ab00566>.

Zbawicka, M., M. I. Trucco, and R. Wenne. 2018. "Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms in Native South American Atlantic Coast Populations of Smooth Shelled Mussels: Hybridization With Invasive European *Mytilus galloprovincialis*." *Genetics, Selection, Evolution* 50: 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-018-0376-z>.

Zhou, X., W.-J. Liao, J.-M. Liao, P. Liao, and H. Lu. 2015. "Ribosomal Proteins: Functions Beyond the Ribosome." *Journal of Molecular Cell Biology* 7, no. 2: 92–104. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jmcb/mjv014>.

Zippay, M. L., and B. Helmuth. 2012. "Effects of Temperature Change on Mussel, *Mytilus*." *Integrative Zoology* 7: 312–327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-4877.2012.00310.x>.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Figure S1:** Geographic locations of 29 mussel sampling sites in Greenland and reference samples of *M. galloprovincialis*, *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus*. See Table 1 for details of site codes, numbers of individuals per location and origin. Map created using ArcGIS Pro 3.2 software (<http://www.esri.com/en-us/arcgis/products/arcgis-pro/overview>). **Figure S2:** Results of the Pearson correlation analysis measuring the strength and direction of the relationship between all studied environmental variables. A correlation of -1.0 indicates a perfect negative correlation, and a correlation of 1.0 indicates a perfect positive correlation among variables. **Figure S3:** Correspondence Analysis of 22 *M. edulis* populations from Greenland. Population codes as shown in Table 1. **Figure S5:** Connection of proportions of *Mytilus* taxa specific SNPs with environmental variables in Greenland. **Figure S4:** Environmental correlates of intraspecific allele distribution in *M. edulis* and *M. trossulus*: an analysis of functional relationships and variable contributions. The appendix presents figures illustrating the standardised relationships between environmental variables and the probability of allele occurrence, with all other variables held at mean levels. The three most important environmental variables in the BRT model are shown. The relative contribution of each environmental variable in the BRT model is given as a percentage next to the variable name. Ascending tick marks on the x-axis represent the frequency of distribution of the data along that dimension. Detailed information on the BRT modelling and the environmental variables involved can be found in the Methods section. **Data S1:** jbi70067-sup-0002-DataS1.xlsx.

Biography

Our research are mainly devoted to molecular genetics, biogeography and the mechanisms of changes in the genetic diversity of the exploited marine and brackish water animals with implications for aquaculture and fishery. Our team combine Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms genotyping with genome and gene expression studies in key marine model fish species and mussels in response to changing marine environmental and ecological factors. Additionally, our team deals with benthic ecology, species interactions, spatial modelling and climate change impacts in marine ecosystems. We are particularly interested in the Arctic environment. Our research are relating to the state of the environment and to environmental protection.